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Creative Writing Curriculum in the Selected Senior High Schools in the Division of Quezon: A Groundwork for a Teaching Guide

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ABSTRACT

The study assessed the level of effectiveness of Creative Writing Curriculum Guide used by teachers of senior high school in the Division of Quezon. Specifically, the study assessed the level of effectiveness of Creative Writing Curriculum Guide in terms of: Content Standard, Performance Standard and Learning Competency. The study used descriptive research design in the presentation of the findings of the study and purposive sampling in the selection of the respondents. There were 30 senior high school teacher-respondents from the selected National Senior High Schools. Although the findings show that the respondent's assessments on the Creative Writing Curriculum Guide in terms of content standard, performance standards and learning competencies were Moderately Effective, there is still a need for improvement in the performance standards based on the general weighted mean. The finding shows that majority of the senior high school students, 532 or 43.04% obtained Satisfactory performance. From the interview, the following challengers emerged: Inappropriate Activities/Task, Learning Material Not Fitting/Confusing, Limited Time, No Teacher's Guide, Lack of Laboratory Rooms, Wi-Fi and Library, Ratio of Teachers with Students, and No monitoring of implementation. There was significant relationship between teachers' strategies in Teaching Creative Writing and content standards, performance standards and learning competency. Based on these, the following are recommended: Strict monitoring on the implementation of the curriculum guide be made to address the needs of the teachers and the students. The authority can use the findings of this study to determine further improvement in teaching Creative Writing and develop the learning competencies of the students as well as improving teacher's performance. The proposed Creative Writing Teaching Guide can be a great help for teachers in meeting the challenges in teaching creative writing.

INTRODUCTION

Traditionally, creative writing is an art of sorts - the art of making things up. It is writing done in a way that is not academic or technical but still attracts an audience. Creative writing can for the most part be considered any writing that is original and self-expressive.

The Department of Education (DEPED) 2013, K-12 Basic Education Curriculum Senior High School-Academic Track for Grade 11 and 12 Creative Writing aims to develop practical and creative skills in reading and writing; introduce students to the fundamental techniques of writing fiction, poetry, and drama; and discuss the use of such techniques by well-known authors in a variety of genres. Each class was devoted to the examination of techniques and to the workshop of students' drafts toward the enrichment of their manuscripts. Students learn how to combine inspiration and revision, and to develop a sense of form.

Ruiz (2012), DepEd Assistant Secretary for Programs and Projects said that school year 2016-2017 would be the first Grade 11 under the K-12. Based on this new program in the Deped the new curriculum was introduced where each subject area has its Curriculum Guide to be used by the teachers. The Creative Writing course of the Senior High School aims to develop practical and creative skills in reading and writing; introduce students to the fundamental techniques of writing fiction, poetry, and drama; and discuss the use of such techniques by well-

known authors in a variety of genres.

The present curriculum guide in Creative Writing serves as a structured document of the teachers in senior high school. In the first column of the guide presents the content that composed of six important topics such as creative writing (imaginative writing, vs. technical/academic / other forms of writing, sensory experience, language, sample works of well-known local and foreign writers) reading and writing poetry, reading and writing fiction, reading and writing drama, the creative work in literary and/or sociopolitical context and the final output. For poetry, fiction, and drama, the workshop proper is highly encouraged. Critiquing of the learner's own work and his/her peers', leading toward revision, is necessary in preparation for the final output. Time allotment may be adjusted based on the learner's phase and capacity.

This paper shows on a textual evaluation of the existing curriculum guide in senior high school Creative Writing under the newly implemented K to 12 Basic Education Program in the Philippines. The study underscores the importance of involving classroom teachers in the processes of creating, selecting, and evaluating curriculum materials, which are considered integral phases in the language-curriculum-development process. Thus, no guide will be perfect, will ever be finished product cast in stone, will be free from criticism, however, to be effective, a guide must earn acceptance by teachers and must be deemed educationally valid by parents and the

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community at large (Connecticut State Department of Education, 2010).

It is also important to reexamine the kind of curriculum that was taken by the respondents during their formative stage, if Creative Writing subject is included in their academic program. It cannot be denied that Creative Writing was only integrated in Literature Subjects in the past but as an independent subject it had never been given emphasis. In writing any literary piece, production is the common way either in written or oral, so a teacher should be an expert. Besides creating is among the highest level of critical thinking, a teacher should have an exceptional talent related to this course; have abundance of experiences particularly in composing these crafts. Any Creative Writing teacher should be full of imagination and can use his/her heart and mind to influence his/her students.

LITERATURE REVIEW

The numerous related literature and studies cited in this present study provided insights and some relevant information on the assessment of the Creative Writing Curriculum Guide for senior high school. Although there are similarities with the present study, the direction either focused on students, teachers and curriculum.

For example, according to Bennett, et al (2008) creative writing can be defined as the study of writing (including poetry, fiction, drama, and creative non-fiction) and its contexts through creative production and reflection on process. By writing we mean not only books and other printed materials, but also scripted and unscripted performances, oral and recorded outputs, and the variety of forms possible in electronic, digital, and other new media. Creative writing can use any form or genre of writing as an exemplary subject of study, but the productions of Creative Writing tend not to be informational, but imaginative interpretations of the world that invite the complex participation of the audience or reader.

Montemayor, Jr., V Benigno C. (2019), also made an assessment of the effectiveness of instruction in the Creative Writing elective at the Philippine Science High School - Main Campus primarily based on the quarterly periodic examination (which are based on novels) results of the CW students, however the focused was on the instruction.

On teaching guide, Rodriguez (2018) adduces that the Teacher's Guide has been developed with the knowledge that there are teachers with little teaching experience as well as teachers with many years of experience. It offers a step-by step outline for how to work through every lesson. Therefore, the primary aim of the Teacher's Guide is to provide teachers, whatever their background, with guidance and suggestions so that they can create successful lesson plans that fulfill their students' needs. In this way, even the least experienced teacher can teach each lesson successfully, and more experienced teachers can make use those activities in the guide that are suitable to their context, with the freedom to deviate from the

Teacher's Guide as they see fit. The present study also intends to propose teaching guide but focused on creative writing for senior high school students.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

The current research utilized the descriptive research design in the assessment of the Creative Writing Curriculum Guide. Although descriptive research has only one meaning, several authors have defined it in their own ways. Some of the definitions are: Aquino (1974) defines Descriptive Research as fact-finding with adequate interpretation. For Manuel and Medel (1976) descriptive research is a method that describes what is. Descriptive Research is defined by Best & Kahn (1998) in this way: It describes and interprets what is. It is concerned with conditions of relationships that exist; practices that reveal; beliefs, processes that are going on, effects that are being felt, or trends that are developing.

This study was conducted in selected National Senior High Schools in the Division of Quezon, Region IV-A. The study used purposive sampling in the selection of the respondents. Among the National Senior High Schools from the Division of Quezon, Region IV-A, the researcher selected schools offering Creative Writing. There were 17 National Senior High Schools offering Creative Writing and 30 teachers given assignment to teach the subject. The researcher requested approval for the conduct of the study from the Schools Division Superintendent of Quezon. Before administering the study, the researcher prepared a questionnaire based on the K to 12 curriculum standards validated by English professors/experts. The researcher utilized a survey adopted from the present K-12 curriculum guide for senior high school, Academic Track. It was modified as per recommended by validators, school principal, K-12- trainers and college professors of creative writing in terms of presentation and scaled used. The study made use of content-validated, reliability-tested, to extract the quantitative databases needed to answer the research questions. The survey-questionnaire consisted of three (3) parts.

Mathematical Expressions and Symbols

The researcher considers the following statistical tools in order to evaluate the Creative Writing Curriculum Guide for senior high school.

1. Mean. To determine the extent of responses of the respondents mean is used. The formula is as follows:

$$\bar{x} = (\sum fx) / n$$

Where:

\bar{x} = mean

$\sum x$ = sum of scores

n = number of respondents

2. Percentage. It is used to identify the most common strategy used by the teachers based on the demand of the curriculum guide and the most challenging problem encountered by the teachers in implementing the creative writing curriculum guide.

The formula is shown below.

$P = (f / N) 100$

Where:

P = percentage

f=frequency

N=total number of respondents

3. For the test of significant relationship, Pearson r test of relationship formula was used:

$$r = \frac{n(\Sigma xy) - (\Sigma x)(\Sigma y)}{\sqrt{[n\Sigma x^2 - (\Sigma x)^2][n\Sigma y^2 - (\Sigma y)^2]}}$$

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Assessments of teachers on the Creative Writing Curriculum Guide in terms of Content Standard, Performance Standard and Learning Competency.

Table 1 shows the respondent’s assessments on creative writing curriculum guide in terms of content standard, performance standards and learning competency. Based on the respondent’s assessments on the creative writing curriculum guide in terms of content standard, the curriculum guide used in creative writing is “Moderately

Table 1: Assessments of teachers on the Creative Writing Curriculum Guide in terms of Content Standard

Content Standard	WM	VI
1. Imaginative Writing The learners have an understanding of imagery, diction, figures of speech, and variations on language	2.43	Moderately Agree
2. Reading and Writing Poetry The learners have an understanding of poetry as a genre and how to analyze its elements and techniques	2.35	Moderately Agree
3. Reading and Writing Fiction The learners have an understanding of fiction as a genre and are able to analyze its elements and techniques	2.40	Moderately Agree
4. Reading and Writing Drama The learners have an understanding of drama as a genre and are able to analyze its elements and techniques	2.00	Moderately Agree
5. The creative work in literary and/or sociopolitical context The learners have an understanding of the different orientations of creative writing	2.30	Moderately Agree
Over-all Mean	2.30	Moderately Agree Moderately Effective

Legend: Disagree / Not Effective (1.00 – 1.49), Moderately Agree/Moderately Effective (1.50 – 2.49), Agree/Effective (2.50 – 3.49), Strongly Agree/Very Effective (3.50 – 4.00)

Effective” with an over-all mean of 2.30.

The DepEd K to 12 Basic Education Curriculum for Senior High School-Academic Track in Creative Writing is for both Grades 11 and 12. The curriculum guide is quite comprehensive—it does not only present the Content but also the Content Standard, Performance Standard, and Learning Competency.

The Content does not identify focal literary works but particularizes on learning topics. For example, in “Reading and Writing Poetry,” there are three subtopics, namely elements of the genre, elements for specific forms, and other experimental texts.

These subtopics are further outlined into two (sometimes three) more levels.

Table 2: Assessments of teachers on the Creative Writing Curriculum Guide in terms of Content Standard

Performance Standard	WM	VI
1. Imaginative Writing The learners can produce short paragraphs or vignettes using imagery, diction, figures of speech, and specific experiences.	2.49	Moderately Agree
2. Reading and Writing Poetry The learners can produce a short, well-crafted poem	2.45	Moderately Agree
3. Reading and Writing Fiction The learners can produce at least one striking scene for a short story	2.50	Moderately Agree
4. Reading and Writing Drama The learners can compose at least one scene for a one-act play that can be staged.	2.50	Moderately Agree
5. The creative work in literary and/or sociopolitical context The learners can produce a craft essay on the personal creative process deploying a consciously selected	2.00	Moderately Agree
Over-all Mean	2.39	Moderately Agree Moderately Effective

Legend: Disagree / Not Effective (1.00 – 1.49), Moderately Agree/Moderately Effective (1.50 – 2.49), Agree/Effective (2.50 – 3.49), Strongly Agree/Very Effective (3.50 – 4.00)

Table 2 illustrates the respondent's assessments on the Creative Writing Curriculum Guide in terms of performance standard. Based on the respondent's assessments on the Creative Writing Curriculum Guide in terms of performance standard, the curriculum guide used in creative writing was "Effective".

According to the Department of Education (2020), expectations for instruction, assessment, and student work are called Performance Standards.

These incorporate Content Standards and define the level of work that demonstrates achievement of the standards. Performance standards isolate and identify skills needed for problem-solving, reasoning, communicating, and making connections with other information. They provide all constituents with the evidences that students have met the content standards, helping teachers define what level of work is satisfactory

Table 3: Assessments of the teachers on the Creative Writing Curriculum Guide in terms of Learning Competency

Learning Competency	WM	VI
1. Imaginative Writing 1.1. Differentiate imaginative writing from other forms of writing 1.2. Cull creative ideas from experiences 1.3. Utilize language to evoke emotional and intellectual responses from readers 1.4. Use imagery, diction, figures of speech, and specific experiences 1.5. Read closely as writers with a consciousness of craft	2.45	Moderately Agree
2. Reading and Writing Poetry 2.1 Identify the various elements, techniques, and literary devices in poetry 2.2 Determine specific forms and conventions of poetry 2.3 Use selected elements of poetry in short exercises 2.4 Explore innovative techniques in writing poetry 2.5 Write a short poem applying the various elements, techniques, and literary devices	2.40	Moderately Agree
3. Reading and Writing Fiction 3.1 Identify the various elements, techniques, and literary devices in fiction 3.2 Determine various modes of fiction 3.3 Write journal entries and other short exercises exploring key elements of fiction 3.4 Write short scene applying the various elements, techniques, and literary devices	2.40	Moderately Agree
4. Reading and Writing Drama 4.1 Identify the various elements, techniques, and literary devices in drama 4.2 Understand intertextuality as a technique of drama 4.3 Conceptualize a character/setting/plot of a one-act play 4.4 Explore different staging modalities vis-à-vis envisioning the script 4.5 Write short exercises involving character, dialogue, plot, and other elements of drama 4.6 Write at least one scene for one-act play applying the various elements, techniques, and literary devices	2.30	Moderately Agree
5. The creative work in literary and/or sociopolitical context 5.1 Situate the creative work in literary and/or sociopolitical context 5.2 Demonstrate awareness of and sensitivity to the different orientations of creative writing 5.3 Write a craft essay	2.00	Moderately Agree
Over-all Mean	2.31	Moderately Agree Moderately Effective

Based on table 3 the assessment on the Creative Writing Curriculum Guide of the teachers' respondents with regard to the aspect of learning competency had a verbal interpretation of "Moderately Effective" with a weighted mean of 2.31.

As to the statement that students recognize the creative writing structure from other types of writing, Richards

(1990) draws attention that writing is a requirement at every level of the students' academic pursuit and is not entirely limited to language and literature. This serves the objective of writing programs, which is to enable the students to produce different kinds of writings. Therefore, creative writing helps to enhance learners' general writing skills.

Table 4: Performance of the Students in Creative Writing

Score	Performance Level	Final Grade Creative Writing	
		f	%
95-100	Outstanding	10	.81
88-94	Very Satisfactory	279	22.57
81-87	Satisfactory	532	43.04

75-80	Fair	346	28
65-74	Poor	69	5.58
Total No. of Students		1236	100%
Average Grade		80.33	Very Satisfactory
SD		4.53	

Students' Performance in Creative Writing based on the Final Grade

Table 4 shows the performance of the 1236 students from selected senior high schools enrolled in Creative Writing based on the general weighted average in the Final Grading Period.

The table shows that majority of the senior high school students, 532 or 43.04% obtained grades between 81 to 87 or Satisfactory performance in Creative Writing. This was followed by 346 or 28% of senior high school students with grade between 75-80, Fair Performance Level in Creative Writing subject.

There were also senior high school students with Outstanding and Very Satisfactory Performance Level

in Creative Writing, 10 or .81% and 279 or 22.57%, respectively. Only 69 or 5.58% of senior high school students who go grades between 65-74 or Poor Performance Level in Creative Writing subject.

In comparison with the statement of Hale (2008) and was quoted by Razalan (2011), Creative Writing is anything where the purpose is to express thoughts, feelings, and emotions rather than to simply convey information. Writing of any sort is hard, but rewarding work. Being creative can also be difficult and challenging at times, but immensely fun.

This helps as an inspiration for the study for the great hopes of the teacher are still there focusing the needs of Creative Writing students.

Table 5: Strategies used by the Teachers in Teaching Creative Writing

Teaching Strategies	WM	VI
1. Imaginative Writing		
1.1 I develop several brainstorming activities for my creative writing class.	4.20	Often
1.2 I use reading aloud to my students for the pleasure of hearing their own work and of getting and giving feedback.	4.00	Often
1.3 I allow students to choose their own genres and topics in response to guided prompts to stimulate ability to write.	4.23	Often
1.4 I use word games to spice-up creative writing lessons.	3.83	Often
1.5 I use word banks to develop creative writing skills of my students.	3.70	Often
2. Reading and Writing Poetry		
2.1 I use quick writes that involve jotting down everything about a topic that students know.	4.03	Often
2.2 I ask students to use rough draft which focus is on finishing.	4.30	Often
2.3 I introduce picture prompts and/or writing prompts.	4.00	Often
2.4 I use Socratic Method for actively engaging students with the critical thinking process.	3.73	Often
2.5 I frequently ask students to take the opening and closing line of a story or poem, carve out the middle, and write a new poem or story.	3.53	Often
3. Reading and Writing Fiction		
3.1 I use visualization (or storyboarding) to distinguish fiction from nonfiction	3.97	Often
3.2 In all writing, fiction and nonfiction, writing needs to go through final editing, so I use this strategy for my student.	4.23	Often
3.3 I create a writing contest where students compete not only against each other but also their peers online too.	3.30	Sometimes
3.4 One of the easiest strategies I use to get students writing is to give them a story starter or writing prompt.	3.83	Often
4. Reading and Writing Drama		
4.1 I use outlining to keep the writer/student focused on moving the writing forward.	4.07	Often
4.2 I ask my students to complete the page in their jotter with as many pieces of detail as they can for their own character. (Characterization)	3.73	Often
4.3 I use narrative distance for the students to experience the character's thoughts.	3.73	Often
4.4 I use workshop to motivate students to be creative and responsible in their own learning.	3.63	Often
4.5 I ask my students group themselves into teams of two, and each student take turns writing down what the other person says. (Peer Talks)	3.57	Often
5. The creative work in literary and/or sociopolitical context		
5.1 I emphasize the importance of research in my class for they can be reused and shared between the genres— they can use it when they think to write.	4.13	Often
5.2 I use journal writing in my class because it is also very helpful at the beginning stages, in getting and developing ideas	3.97	Often

5.3 I find video clips of a writer whose work they are using as a model in the class	3.83	Often
5.4 Through audio transcription my students may print out what they just wrote, and use that as their first draft.	3.10	Sometimes
Grand Mean	3.84	Often

Common strategies used by the teachers in teaching Creative Writing based on the present curriculum guide

Based on the K-12 Basic Education Creative Writing Course for Senior High School (2014) under the Academic Track, that students should develop competency in creative skills in terms of: imaginative writing, reading and writing poetry; reading and writing fiction, reading

and writing drama and creative work in literary and/or socio-political context. The teachers shared the common strategies they used in teaching creative writing in the absence of the teaching guide. Based on the profile of the teachers, not all teachers specialized in creative writing. However, some of the teachers have specialization in English and Linguistic with more than three (3) years of experience in teaching English and other subjects.

Table 6: Relationship between Assessment of the Teachers in the Creative Writing Curriculum Guide and the Common Strategies they Used

Common Strategies					
Indicators	Strategies	Description	P-value	Decision	Remarks
Content Standard	0.444	Substantial Correlation	0.014	Reject Ho	Significant
Performance Standard	0.369	Low Correlation	0.045	Reject Ho	Significant
Learning Competencies	0.450	Substantial Correlation	0.013	Reject Ho	Significant

0.00 - ± 0.20 Negligible Correlation 0.41 - ± 0.70 Substantial Correlation
 0.21 - ± 0.40 Low Correlation 0.71 - ± 1.00 High Correlation
 Correlation is significant at 0.01 level

Relationship between Teachers Assessment of the Creative Writing Curriculum Guide and the Common Strategies they used

Based on the result, content standard, performance standard and learning competency have significant relationship with common strategies used by the teachers since the p-value are 0.014, 0.045, and 0.013, respectively, which is less than the level of significance (0.05).

Therefore, the researcher has sufficient evidence to conclude that there is significant relationship between the assessment of the teachers in the creative writing CG and the common strategies used by the teachers. Moreover, since the substantial correlations that exist on content standard, performance standard and learning competencies are positive; this means that these three indicators are directly related to the common strategies used by the teachers.

Challenges encountered by creative writing teachers using the Curriculum Guide

The teacher-respondents identified the following challenges: unavailable teaching guide unappropriated activities/tasks, insufficient authentic language, learning materials not fitting, confusing, limited time, lack of laboratory and equipment. Other challengers were: language tasks in the curriculum guide do not match the need to develop learners’ multilingual, multicultural, and media-literacy skills.

On objectives, the teachers found them and stated in a language not clear for both teachers and learners. Finally, the format of the curriculum guide presented, the teachers responded that confused the teachers and did not directly establish an affinity with other important materials such

as the modules provided by the DepEd.

The Proposed Applicable Teaching Guide for Creative Writing in Senior High School

Because the present curriculum guide in creative writing has no existing teaching guide the researcher attempts to develop a teacher’s guide related to the most essential learning competencies passed by the DepEd that can be used in Senior High School.

CONCLUSIONS

Based on the findings, the following conclusions were drawn: the existing Creative Writing Curriculum Guide needs further improvement in the three categories: of content standard, performance standards and learning competency as revealed by a Moderately Effective assessment. Majority of the senior high school students grades in the Creative Writing subject clustered along 81 to 87 or satisfactory performance. The teachers shared the common strategies they used in teaching creative writing in the absence of the teaching guide. The teachers of Creative Writing were challenged by: Inappropriate Activities/Task, Learning Material Not Fitting/Confusing, Limited Time, No Teacher’s Guide, Lack of Laboratory Rooms, Wi-Fi and Library, Ratio of Teachers with Students, and No monitoring of implementation. There was significant relationship between teachers’ strategies in teaching creative writing and content standards, performance standards and learning competencies. The proposed guide in teaching Creative Writing may be of great help to teachers.

Based on the findings and conclusions, the following are recommendations given: Firstly, strict monitoring on the implementation of the curriculum guide be made to address the needs of the teachers and the students. The school principals and heads can use the findings of this study to determine further improvement in teaching

creative writing and develop the learning competencies of the students. The strategies used by the teachers may be used as reference in crafting teaching for Creative Writing. The Department Heads should address or solve the challenges of the teachers in teaching Creative Writing. Since there is a relationship in the teacher's assessment of the curriculum guide and strategies used by the teachers, this can be a great help in improving the teacher's performance as well as the learning competency of the students through a teaching guide. Implementation the use of principals and heads of the English Department may of Creative Writing Teaching Guide which can be a great help for teachers in meeting the challenges in teaching Creative Writing as crafted by the researcher. Lastly, future researchers to conduct similar studies along teaching effectiveness in English.

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